

REPOSITORIES & IF

SESSION I

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THE IMPACT FACTOR (IF)

is a measure of the frequency with which the average article in a journal has been cited in a particular year.

OPEN REPOSITORIES

A free online collection of documents, often scholarly.

Impact Factor

PREPARED BY RANIA BALEELA

What

Is it?

A MEASURE

of journal influence

IF

or

JIF

is a

SCIENTOMETRIC INDEX

calculated by Clarivate

**Supposed
to**

**Reflects the yearly average
number of citations to recent
articles published in a journal.**

Frequently used as a proxy for the
relative importance of a journal
within its field.

1960s Impact factor

invented by the librarian and linguist Eugene Garfield
A rough calculation of how often papers in a given journal are cited in other papers.

“like nuclear energy ... a mixed blessing”

Eugene Garfield... the founder of the Institute for Scientific Information (ISI).

Calculations

JIF for a journal for the year 2021 =

number of citations in 2021 to articles from
journal issues in 2020 and 2019

the number of articles that actually
appeared in the journal in 2020 and 2019

The numerator in this function includes citations to every single article that appeared in the journal over the course of those two years, but the denominator only includes certain types of articles.

Are published annually in the **Journal Citation Reports** which are marketed as a **commercial product**.

Are calculated on the basis of the journals listed in the multidisciplinary citation database "**Web of Science**" from the so called "Core Collection" and the citation frequencies recorded in the database= therefore **only represents a portion of the world's journals and not all the academic journal titles published worldwide**.

The citation frequency is determined by the citations in the **Web of Science database** rather than all **conceivable citations**.

Revenue US\$2.66 billion (2022)

- Web of Science
- EndNote
- Journal Citation Reports
- Derwent

The JIF cannot be calculated for a journal until it has been in the Web of Science for at least three years.

Was originally developed to assist libraries in selecting the best journals to subscribe to in their subject areas. That means it is ultimately a **tool** for evaluating academic journals

Criticism of the JIF

1. It should not be used to evaluate the research work of scientists and academics.
2. The frequency with which articles are cited is not an indication of the quality of a journal and the articles it contains. It is only an indication of a scholarly article's impact, and not as a solid assessment of the quality of the results themselves.
3. The Journal Citation Reports with the Journal Impact Factors for each year are always issued in the summer of the following year and are based on the two years that precede the reporting year.
4. JIF is statistically inappropriate. In addition, the JIF is not 'normalised' across disciplines

5. The default citation window of two years is too short to judge the impact of publications in many disciplines.
6. JIF is susceptible to manipulation (can be artificially boosted by journals citing their own articles).
7. The citation impact of a journal also depends on which types of documents it publishes e.g. review articles are cited significantly more frequently than other types). Thus, journals that publish lots of review articles can increase their citation count and raise their impact factor.

These criticisms mean that a JIF is not adequate as the sole metric for selecting a journal, and is certainly not a suitable means of evaluating the work of individual scientists.

Other citation-based metrics and altmetrics

- SCImago Journal Rank (SJR)
- Source Normalized Impact per Paper (SNIP)
- h-index or Hirsch index
- Alternative Metrics: Altmetrics

Publishers with alternative metrics

PLOS ONE

Wiley

Taylor & Francis

Repositories

PRESENTED BY
RANIA BALEELA
OPEN SCIENCE TRAINER

“Everyone has the right to freedom of opinion and expression; this right includes freedom to hold opinions without interference and to seek, receive and impart information and ideas through any media and regardless of frontiers.”

Article 19

**Open
Repository =
Open-access
Repository**

PHOTO BY JAMES LEE

The What?

- It is a free online collection of documents, often scholarly.
- It provides:

**A CENTRALIZED
DIGITAL STORAGE**

FREE

IMMEDIATE

PERMANENT

THE WHY?

ACCESS TO KNOWLEDGE

- Advances research and innovation
- Improves decision-making
- Exposes misinformation and is vital to achieving greater equality and justice.

PHOTO BY PHIL

REPOSITORIES THAT FACILITATE OA ARE:

- **Interoperable** according to the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH).
- The cornerstone for **FAIR** data practices and are used expeditiously within the scientific community.

DISCONTINUED

At Santa Fe Convention for the Open Archives Initiative (February 15th 2000)

(TECHNICAL & ORGANIZATIONAL FRAMEWORK)

Concern were:

- that archives would needlessly replicate each other's content,
- users would have to learn multiple interfaces in order to use them.

It was therefore felt there was a need to develop tools and protocols that would allow repositories to copy content from each other, and to work in concert on a distributed basis.

= **birth of the OAI-PMH**

OAI-PMH

A protocol developed for harvesting metadata descriptions of records in an archive so that services can be built using metadata from many archives.

THE BENEFITS OF OA REPOSITORIES ARE:

1. Openness
2. Maximum visibility and impact
3. Showcasing
4. Collecting and curating digital output
5. Managing and measuring research and teaching activities
6. Providing a workspace
7. Enabling and encouraging interdisciplinary approaches
8. Facilitating the development and sharing of digital teaching materials

3 COMMON TYPES OF DIGITAL REPOSITORIES:

institutional

disciplinary

commercial

**Self-archiving or "Green"
route to open access through:**

- 1. Institutional repository**
- 2. Disciplinary repository**

PHOTO BY RUNZE SHI

INSTITUTIONAL REPOSITORIES

TO THOSE AFFILIATED WITH THE
INSTITUTION

- Provide free access to research for users outside the institutional community
- One of the recommended ways to achieve the OA vision

DISCIPLINARY / SUBJECT REPOSITORIES

A research database containing materials related to a particular subject area

- Encourage scholars from multiple institutions to post research in specific fields of scholarship.**

Afric ArXiv

AfricArxiv is a community-led digital archive for African research items such as research manuscripts, reports, datasets, code, illustrations, presentations, and more. It enhances the visibility of African research, enables discoverability and collaboration opportunities for African scientists on the continent as well as globally.

Open Science

Open Science grassroots initiatives

 Kumu / Feb 17, 2020

**This map is based on and inspired by
<https://101innovations.wordpress.com/>
For comments, questions and suggestions
please email
info@access2perspectives.org or tweet at
[@openscicomm](https://twitter.com/openscicomm)**

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... TO BENEFIT SOCIETY AND THE PLANET.

**To check for a repository
in your discipline try
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Disciplinary repositories

 This list is part of the [Open Access Directory](#).

- This is a list of OA disciplinary repositories (also called central or subject repositories). Unless otherwise noted, they accept relevant deposits regardless of the author's institutional affiliation.
- This list includes both preprint and postprint repositories.
- When possible, please indicate the institution hosting or maintaining the repository. If a repository only accepts submissions in certain languages, please indicate the languages. If a repository is open in some respects but not others, please include it with an annotation rather than exclude it.
- For a bibliography of works on disciplinary repositories, see the section on [Disciplinary Archives](#) in the [OAD Bibliography of open access](#).
- Related lists in OAD: [Data repositories](#).
- Also see the [Wikipedia list of preprint repositories](#), organized by field or discipline.
- For news about disciplinary repositories, including some newly launched repositories not yet listed here, follow the [oa.repositories.disciplinary](#) tag of the [Open Access Tracking Project](#).
- Wikidata identifier for this page: [Q56229148](#).
- Alphabetical by field.

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OPEN ACCESS DIRECTORY

bioRxiv

THE PREPRINT SERVER FOR BIOLOGY

[Advanced Search](#)

COVID-19 SARS-CoV-2 preprints from medRxiv and bioRxiv

Subject Areas

[All Articles](#)

[Animal Behavior and Cognition](#)

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re3data.org

(THE REGISTRY OF RESEARCH DATA REPOSITORIES)

Browse by country

Graphical Text

Browse by subject

Example of search results

Graphical Text

click to zoom into subjects or to select a bottommost subject in the hierachy as filter for the re3data search page
shift + click on a top subject to select it as filter

Browse by content type

- Archived data
- Audiovisual data
- Configuration data
- Databases
- Images
- Networkbased data
- Plain text
- Raw data
- Scientific and statistical data formats
- Software applications
- Source code
- Standard office documents
- Structured graphics
- Structured text
- other

FREE

OPENALEX

1. Dissertations and Theses (examples):

[Digital Commons Networks \(Bepress\)](#)

[Electronic Dissertations and Theses Collection \(University of North Carolina\)](#)

[UNISA Institutional Repository](#)

[The Open University](#)

[DART-Europe E-theses Portal](#)

2. ISSN, Funders, etc:

SHERPA/JULIET

Welcome to the new look
Sherpa Services

Our new site consolidates Sherpa Services ([Romeo](#), [Juliet](#), [Fact](#)) in to one handy tool. With the addition of [Open Access Books](#), [Open Access compliance](#) and [Transitional Agreement look-up](#) tools.

Search across Sherpa Services

Search for a journal, publisher, funder or repository. For open access book policies, search for a publisher below.

3. The British Library

Consult the collection

Search our online catalogue to find most of our printed collections and some freely available online resources, but not everything is available.

[Search the catalogue](#)

Use the Library

Our Reading Rooms in London and Yorkshire are open, but access to our collection and online resources is limited.

[What you can do](#)

Visit our buildings

Our buildings in London and Yorkshire are open as usual. Find our opening hours, facilities and access information.

[Visiting us](#)

Attend an event

Find schools information

Get business support